

QUIZ**LAST NAME: MUBANGA****FIRST NAME: RAPHAEL****PROGRAM CODE : DSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: SIX****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 8.1)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Which one of the following is an example of plagiarism?

- Citing your own previous work
- Paraphrasing someone else's ideas or words
- Having someone write part of your paper¹**
- Quoting exactly as in the source

2. Which one of the following should not be included when citing a print source using the Chicago (Turabian) citation style?

- Date
- URL²**

¹ Cleenewerck Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 5.

² Laurent and Gulma, 53.

- Author's name
- Title

3. **When is it not necessary to cite?**

- When the ideas are from your previous work
- When you just borrow ideas from a source but write it in your own words
- When the information you are writing about is common knowledge and can be found in numerous sources³**
- When you paraphrase the sentence to differentiate it from the source

4. **When and why do we do qualitative research?**

- When we perceive a problem, or some unsatisfactory situation that we want to confront⁴**
- When there is little information in the literature on the subject
- When we are interested in a certain topic
- When we have a feeling about something and we want to go and prove it

5. **In qualitative research, how should the research questions be?**

- Should be interpretive, and theoretical⁵**

³ Laurent and Gulma, 9–10.

⁴ Linda Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (California: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2008), 34.

⁵ Bloomberg and Volpe, 37.

- Should solicit for yes or no answers
 - Should be directional
 - Should imply cause and effect, or suggest some measurement
6. **Which one of the following is NOT true about delimitations and limitations?**
- As a researcher, you have powers to control the delimitations
 - Not all studies have limitations, especially if you are careful⁶**
 - Limitations expose the conditions that may weaken the study
 - Restricted sample size and sample selection are typical examples of limitations
7. **Which one is TRUE about research questions in a qualitative research before you get deep into your project?**
- You can imagine some plausible answers, but they have to be based on evidence and facts
 - You can imagine some plausible answers, as long as you know they will turn out to be correct at the end of the study
 - You can imagine some plausible answers, no matter how speculative they may be⁷**
 - Do not imagine any plausible answers until you conduct your research
8. **Which one of the following is correct about the literature review?**

⁶ Bloomberg and Volpe, 78–79.

⁷ Kate L Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th Edition (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 19.

- Include information that only agrees with your views
 - You should not offer opposite perspective to the idea if it was written by a prominent researcher
 - Include both creative agreement and disagreement⁸**
 - You have to include all the information you come across
9. **Which one of the following is NOT true about brackets in academic and professional writing?**
- Round brackets can be used instead of commas when the texts they contain has lower emphasis
 - Round and square brackets are used interchangeably⁹**
 - Square brackets are used to make insertions in the quoted material
 - Square brackets can be used to insert translation
10. **Which one of the following is NOT true about numbering?**
- It is fine to start a sentence with a figure¹⁰**
 - Low numbers up to nine should be spelled out while larger numbers, ten and above should be written in figures
 - You should always use figures for statistics regardless of how small or large the numbers may be
 - Always use figures with units of measurement that are denoted by symbol or abbreviations

⁸ Turabian, 30–31; Laurent and Gulma, 2.

⁹ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 7th ed. (Luxembourg: Office of the Directorate-General for Translation, 2011), 19.

¹⁰ European Commission, 22–25.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
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